

Sign Language Recognition: Can depth cameras be used to correct Mediapipe errors?

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Abstract

Mediapipe is increasingly deployed in Sign Language Recognition (SLR) pipelines. This paper highlights errors in Mediapipe that adversely affect the performance of these models. The use of depth cameras has been intuitively proposed for the correction of depth estimation errors. We propose a Mediapipe input pre-processing technique using depth sensor data specifically tailored for SLR systems. However, our experimental results show that such techniques are problematic owing to the inherent distortion in depth sensor output.

Keywords: Mediapipe, Depth Camera, Image Pre-processing, Sign Language Recognition, Computer Vision

1 Introduction and background

Sign Language Recognition (SLR) models are used to identify the phonetic elements of signs, one of which is the articulated hand shape [Rastgoo et al., 2021]. Mediapipe is a pose estimation model that outputs the 3D coordinates of the hand finger-tips and skeletal joints from an RGB image. These hand pose vectors can be used as feature descriptors in deep learning SLR models. Any errors in the Mediapipe output are propagated through the rest of the recognition pipeline. This paper describes an experimental approach to correct Mediapipe pose keypoint errors by using images from a depth sensor. The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the two main types of error in Mediapipe output. Section 3 describes a technique to correct such errors and Section 4 summarises the results and gives a conclusion.

1.1 Related work

Classification of Sign Language articulations is a difficult task because of the complex handshapes and signing speed of native signers [Bragg et al., 2019]. Pose models have been used successfully to extract features as part of Sign Language Recognition (SLR) pipelines [Wadhawan, A. & Kumar, P., 2021]. The top performing model in the Kaggle Isolated American Sign Language (ASL) Recognition competition achieved an accuracy of 89% using Mediapipe for feature extraction [Kaggle, 2023]. The performance limit due to the inherent class confusion of visually similar signs has been reported [Fowley et al., 2022].

2 MediaPipe errors

Errors due to self-occluded hand poses: The matrix in figure 1 displays the average cosine similarity between classes of poses abstracted by Mediapipe from a dataset of fingerspelling signs signed by native signers. Each class sample is represented as a 63-element vector made up of the 3D coordinates of the 21 skeletal keypoints of the pose. The values circled in red represent visual similarities between some hand shapes, for example, between “M” and “N”, and “U” and “V”. The figure shows additional class confusion, not evident in the latent space of fingerspelling handshapes, due to Mediapipe prediction errors. They are highlighted in yellow and are class confusion between “S” and “M” or “N”, and between “E” and “O”. On closer inspection of the actual sample poses, it is seen that

Figure 1: Sign Language class similarity matrix

Mediapipe mis-calculates the Z coordinate of these samples. This has the effect of “squeezing” the fingers of the “O” pose into an “E” pose and has brought the thumb backwards in the “S” pose to become an “N” pose. The above are errors in the YZ plane or depth plane in the 3D pose predictions. There are also errors in the frontal elevation or XY plane of the poses.

Errors due to other skin texture behind the hand: The output poses in figure 2 show that the skin texture of the face behind the hand is causing Mediapipe errors, with some fingertips appearing at the cheek and ear locations. In the case of the ‘N’ and ‘R’ examples, their errored poses are those of ‘A’ and ‘U’ and would result in this mis-classification by any subsequent SLR model.

Figure 2a: ‘A’, ‘B’, ‘N’, ‘D’, ‘S’ Errors

Figure 2b: ‘N’ Errors

Figure 2c: ‘R’ Errors

Figures 2b and 2c show the erroneous effect for the ‘N’ Sign handshape as it moves in front of the face. The Mediapipe pose is correct before it is in front of the face. The errored thumb location gets progressively worse as it moves across the skin texture of the face. The three incorrect ‘N’ poses would be confused for the ‘A’ handshape whilst the errored ‘R’ pose would be mis-classified as a ‘U’.

3 Using depth sensors to correct Mediapipe errors

In order to correct such Mediapipe errors in the Z coordinate of the pose keypoints, an obvious solution is to use a depth camera to obtain the Z coordinate value directly at the computer vision capture stage of the SLR pipeline.

Intel RealSense depth sensor: The Intel RealSense D435 device is a structured-light stereo-vision infra-red laser depth camera [Intel, 2023]. It incorporates a colour camera with up to 1920 x 1080 RGB pixel resolution, an infra-red (IR) 850 nanometre laser projector and two Full-HD resolution depth sensors with up to 1280 x 720 stereo depth resolution. It operates at up to 90 frames-per-second streaming with a wide depth diagonal field-of-view of over 90 degrees and a range of 0.2 metres to over 3 metres. The depth image pixel value represents the distance in metres from the camera to the object surface in the camera view. The image processing on the device allows captured depth and colour images to be pixel-wise aligned and their streams synchronised. This allows for the Mediapipe keypoint pixel coordinates in the colour image to be “de-projected” into world-space 3D coordinates using the depth image.

Depth sensor noise and de-noising techniques: Depth sensors are susceptible to the following types of image distortion [Grunnet-Jepsen & Tong, 2018]. *Shadow* is due to the triangulation technique used to accurately determine the depth when using dual-receivers. *Holes* result in the appearance of black pixel values caused by low-confidence depth calculations, camera occlusion and over-exposure. *Edges* are due to reflectivity blur around edges. *Jitter* is caused by surface reflectivity differences across the textures of IR-illuminated objects in the view. The above can be seen as black edge distortion and noise on the unfiltered examples shown in figures 3 and 6. De-noising is achieved by filtering which smooths out isolated incorrect pixel values [Tadic et al, 2020]. Edge-preserving low-pass filters can remove the high-frequency noise appearing at edges while maintaining edge definition. Hole-filling techniques use nearest neighbour pixels to fill the missing hole value. Figure 3 shows the effectiveness of de-noising when applied to the process of hand segmentation. The de-noising filtering and smoothing functions in the Realsense SDK were applied to the sensor output for all our experiments.

Figure 3: The effect of de-noising on hand segmentation for the ‘5’ and ‘S’ shapes showing the raw depth image and segmented hand image. The clearer images are de-noised.

4 Proposed image processing method

The proposed pre-processing method uses two techniques to correct Mediapipe errors using aligned depth images.

To correct the Mediapipe depth error (Y-Z plane error): The Realsense sensor incorporates an RGB camera, the frames from which can be used as input to Mediapipe to provide 3D pose data. The corresponding aligned depth frame is used to improve the Z value of these landmark estimates.

Figure 4: Depth correction pre-processing method.

The technique is to firstly “de-project” the keypoint XY pose estimate from the Mediapipe pixel coordinates to real-world units and use the depth map value as the Z coordinate instead of the pose model estimated depth value. This is intended to “correct” the Z coordinate of the pose model predicted value with the actual depth value.

To correct the Mediapipe skin texture error (X-Y plane error): We propose a novel hand segmentation technique to reduce confusion from other body parts appearing behind the hand in the camera view. This “depth-segmentation” assumes that the image pixel point with the minimum depth, will be on the “dominant” signing hand which will be the body part nearest to the camera.

Figure 5: The image processing stages (a) through (f)

It can be further assumed that the signing hand will appear in a limited field-of-depth behind this minimum depth point in the “signing space”. The colour pixels are blacked out in the RGB image corresponding to the depth image pixels that are not in the hand field-of-depth. This effectively segments the hand field-of-depth contour in the colour image. This reduces the likelihood that there is another skin-textured body part in the input to Mediapipe. This process is outlined in Figure 5. The

denoised raw depth image (a) is first depth-segmented by zeroing or blackening the pixels not within the signing space depth field (b). The min-depth of the image is assumed to be on the hand. Using a field-of-depth from this min-depth, the hand is segmented in the depth image (c). The largest contour in this image is then abstracted (d) and its bounding box is used to crop the hand in the corresponding colour image (e) which is aligned with the depth image. The contour in (d) is also used to segment the hand in the colour image (f).

5 Experimental results

While there were some improvements in specific hand shape pose estimation by Mediapipe, the overall results demonstrated that the use of depth images to improve Mediapipe performance is problematic. Two main obstacles in the success of our proposed pre-processing are the following.

Figure 6: Residual depth image noise.

Residual depth image distortion: Despite de-noising and pre-processing methods applied, some images contained distortion at the edges of the segmented hand. For any predicted keypoints on XY pixel locations that are close to the edge of the hand in such an image, the de-projected depth value in that noise area will be a corrupted or zero valued. This effect can be seen in figure 6. On the left of the

figure, one of the pinky bone’s end is located in edge noise which will have an incorrect de-projected Z (depth) value. Similarly for the thumb tip in the right of the figure.

Mediapipe tracking issue: Mediapipe ‘tracking’ enables the pose estimation model to use previously streamed frames to temporally improve its accuracy. In order to evaluate whether our pre-processing technique results in improved Mediapipe pose estimations, we measured the resulting skeletal bone lengths of the corrected poses and compared them with the actual bone lengths of the tester. The tests were conducted on eight ASL handshape phonemes and are summarised in the charts in figure 7. The results show that the cropping and segmentation do not

lead to improvement in pose estimation. The bone lengths are more accurate when using the full colour images with Mediapipe. The change in Mediapipe input image size and resolution due to the cropping and segmentation counteract the Mediapipe tracking and results in a decrease in Mediapipe accuracy.

Figure 7: Average bone lengths for 8 pose-sets. Left: cropped hand images. Right: segmented hand images

Figure 7 shows the average hand bone lengths for 8 pose recordings of the ‘A’, ‘B’, ‘D’, ‘S’, ‘N’, ‘R’, ‘5’, ‘CLAW’ hand shapes. The vertical values are the stacked average lengths for each of the 20 hand bones. The bone lengths for the ‘5’ handshape approximates the ground truth. The results show that the Mediapipe output for full colour image input is the most consistent and accurate. The cropped segmented hand images have blackening out behind-the-hand skin

texture pixels. However, the noise in the depth images causes the contour segmentation of the depth images to be unstable.

6 Conclusion

We have conducted an in-depth analysis of Mediapipe errors which cause mis-classifications in Sign Language Recognition models specifically. We have carried out initial investigation into mitigation measures that could be used to correct such errors. The results show that further research and experimentation is needed to provide an effective pre-processing pose correction pipeline.

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